

Effect of Dietary Incorporation of Sorghum Straw on Performance and Carcass Characteristics of Sudanese Desert Lambs (Shuguor Ecotype)

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Abstract

Twenty-seven entire lambs of Sudan desert sheep Shuguor ecotype 5.6 months of age and their average body weight (23.40kg) were used to evaluate the effect of dietary incorporation of different level of Sorghum Straw (SS) in a fattening experiment which extended for sixty days. Experimental animals were fed iso-caloric and iso-nitrogenous diets containing 0% (control), 20% and 30% SS for A, B and C treatments respectively. The lambs randomly divided into three groups A, B and C each group content 9 animals, then each group was randomly sub divided into three groups of three animals each (replicates) with similar average body weight (23.40 kg). lamb's feedlot performance and carcass characteristics data were statistically analyzed by analyses of variance applicable to completely randomized designs (CRD). The study showed no significant differences ($P \geq 0.05$) among the different experimental groups for initial body weight (IBW), daily feed intake (DFI) and daily feed intake as % of live body weight, shoulder, loin, breast fat and connective tissues as percentage of hot carcass weight while the study observed high significant differences ($P \leq 0.01$) among the different experimental groups for hot carcass weight(HCW), dressing percentage on live body weight(D%LBW) , dressing percentage on empty body weight (D%EBW), leges , muscles and bone as percentage of hot carcass weight. It was concluded that the

addition of SS up to 30% lead to satisfactory feedlot performance and carcass yield. Due to results the study recommended to use ration incorporated 20% SS for fattening desert lambs.

Keywords: *Sorghum Straw, Shugyor Breed, Meat Production, Total body Weight Gain and Daily Feed intake.*

Suggested citation: Mohammed, H.S.T., Tameem Eldar, A.A., Hassan, H.E., Elhashmi, Y.H.A., Abdelmageed, M.E.I., Mohammed, M.A.S., Morkaz, M.G., Idam, O.A., Hussein, B.E., & Sahal, K.E. (2025). Effect of Dietary Incorporation of Sorghum Straw on Performance and Carcass Characteristics of Sudanese Desert Lambs (Shugyor Ecotype). *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 2(6), 225-232. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2025.2(6).21

Introduction

Sudan is the African's largest country, with nearly one million square miles area, extending from 4° to 22° north and 22° to 38° east. It has one of the largest livestock populations in the continent. The numbers of livestock species were 52.80, 43.44, 41.67 and 4.62 for sheep, goats, cattle and camels respectively (FAO, 2015). Livestock in the Sudan satisfies the internal demand and share widely for export, which represents about 22% of the country's total exports. Livestock industry is one of greatest importance to Sudanese economy as it is one of the main sources of food, employment and foreign currency. According to Hamid (2015) and (M.A.R.F,2010) provided official estimation of the size of Sudan's livestock population currently are 52.08 million of sheep, 43.44 million of goats, 41.67 million of cattle and 4.62 million of camels. Steven, (2009) reported that, nutrition plays a major role in the overall productivity, health, and well-being of the sheep flock. Nutrient requirements of sheep are varied with differences in age, body weight, and stage of production. The five major categories of nutrients required by sheep are water, energy, protein, vitamins and minerals. The nutritional management of the animal can affect meat quality and weight, carcass yield and retail cuts, which are extremely important for measuring the animal process of meat production (Lage *et al.*, 2014). Non - traditional by-products of the agricultural industry are a potentially valuable alternative source of animal feed which may decrease dependence on traditional feed products and decrease overall feeding costs Gomes *et al.* (2012). Many authors interested on wide scale searching on utilization and output of using different types of agricultural by- products for feeding Sudanese desert lambs to improve animal performance and meat characteristics and reported satisfy results (Beshir, 1996, Ali, 2003, Beshir *et al.*, 2009, Abd Elgadeem, 2019, Mohana, 2018 Hagam,2020, Babiker, 2020 Ibrahim, 2020, Hassan *et. al.*,2024 and Mohammed *et. al.*, 2024) on fattening and finishing lamb. The results of these studies indicated the high potentiality in fattening animals and improve the meat characteristics.

Study Justifications

High costs of feed inputs, in addition of availability of agricultural by- products such as groundnut hay, sesame hay, maize straw and other agricultural by- products in wide scale utilized in the process of feeding animals but not in scientific way within lack and lower standard of farm animal feed quality control.

Objectives of the Study

This study is designed to evaluate effect of using different levels of Sorghum straw on performance of Sudan desert sheep (Shugyor- ecotype) as general objective while the specific objectives were:

1. To evaluate effect of using different levels of Sorghum straw on lambs' performance and economic study of experimental rations.
2. To evaluate effect of feeding different levels of Sorghum straw on sheep meat quality attributes.

Materials and Methods

Site of the Study

This study was conducted at the Rural Development and Extension Center (R.D.E.C), Faculty of Animal Production – Al-Managil- University of Gezira; 76 kilometers west to Wad Madani, Gezira state (Sudan). The experiment extended for 60 days.

Experimental Animal Housing

Experimental animals were kept in a house which was 9×15 m, bounded by metal sheets 2 m in height set over a half meter brick wall. The house was divided internally into 9 pens, beside other empty spaces were left as service area. Each pen (1.5×3 m) has a separate door and equipped with a metal feed trough and a plastic water container. The roof was made of corrugated metal sheets, slopping from the middle (3-2.5 m) to the side, supported with metal pipes. The ground was made of concrete with reasonable inclination for drainage.

Experimental Animals

Twenty-seven male lambs of Sudan desert sheep (Shugur ecotype), were used. The animals were selected according to their age (5-6 months) and their average body weight (23.40 kg). They were transported to AL-Managil city by truck and they were kept in (R.D.E.C). Animals were vaccinated against anthrax and hemorrhagic septicemia. They were ear tagged, drenched with (ELbendazol -25) to treat internal parasites. Acaricide was applied externally to kill and drop away external parasites. Oxytetracycline injections. were also given to treat subclinical infections. Animals were allowed 15 days as adaptation period.

Experimental Rations

Sorghum Straw preparation

Sorghum straw (SS) as sorghum grain by- products was collated after harvesting operation during end of season. Sorghum straws was chopped, crushed and backed in nylon sacs and storage for dry season to be use. A sample of Sorghum straw chemically was analyzed according to Association of Official Analytical Chemists AOAC, (1980) as the following.

Table 1. Chemical Composition (on Dry Matter Basis) of Sorghum Straw

Items	Percentage
Dry matter "D.M"	95.50
Crude protein "C.P"	6.95
Crude fiber "C.F"	12.15
Ether extract "E.E"	2.25
Ash	11.10

Ration formulation

Three experimental rations were formulated using Sorghum straw (SS). **Table (2)** and other ingredient include Sorghum grain, groundnut cake wheat bran, groundnut hulls, groundnut hay, and molasses, Urea, Caco3 and NaCl.

Ration preparing and chemical analysis

Sorghum straw was prepared and liquid urea and molasses was added beside other different ration ingredients groundnut cake, groundnut hulls, wheat bran, sorghum grain, and common salt (2). The ration was then dried under shade and stored in labeled plastic sacks. The ration formulated to attain 14.10% CP (DM) and 10.60ME MJ/Kg).

Table 2. Experimental Rations Formulation (%)

Sorghum straw levels Item	Experimental Grouping		
	A Control (SS)0%	B (SS) 20%	C (SS) 30%
Sorghum straw	0.00	20.00	30.00
Sorghum grain	12.65	7.00	6.00
Ground nut cake	5.00	4.00	7.00
Wheat bran	16.00	14.00	6.00
Ground nut hay	20.00	0.00	0.00
Ground nut hulls	21.00	31.00	30.00
Molasses	20.00	18.00	15.00
Urea	1.35	2.00	2.00
Oyster shell	2.00	2.00	2.00
NaCl	2.00	2.00	2.00
Total	100.00	100.00	100.00

Table 3. Chemical Composition (Dry Matter Basis) of Experimental Rations

Sorghum Straw Levels Items	Experimental Grouping		
	A (Control SS 0%)	B (SS 20%)	C (SS 30%)
Dry matter "D.M"	93.5	92.5	94.5
Crude protein "C.P"	16.05	15.95	15.85
Crude fiber "C.F"	8.70	9.30	9.45
Ether extract "E.E"	4.55	4.25	4.35
Ash	9.15	8.75	9.15
ME (MJ/kg DM)	10.60	10.60	10.60

Adaptation period

During this period, which extended for two weeks the experimental animals were fed with experimental rations, shown in Table (2) and which contained (16.05%, 15.95% and 15.85 % crude protein) and (10.60 and 10.60 and 10.60 MJ/Kg metabolism energy) for both A, B and C respectively. The rations were given to the lambs daily every morning at 8:00 am and the refusal part was collected in the next morning at 7:00 am

Data Collection

Feed intake: The rations were given to the lambs daily every morning at 8:00 am and the refusal part was collected in the next morning at 7:00 am, weighed and subtracted from the daily offered amount to calculate the actual feed intake.

Body weight: The experimental animals were weekly weighed by using small ruminant's balance (0-50 kg capacity), following an overnight fasting. The body weights were used to calculate the daily weight gain and feed conversion ratio (F.C.R).

Carcass data and carcass cuts

The carcasses were weighed warm and then separated into wholesale cuts according to procedure outlined by Smith (1988) as follows and weighed

- 1. Neck:** The neck was removed by cutting through the junction of sixth and seventh vertebrae.
- 2. Loin:** The loin was obtained by cutting between the 12th and 13th rib, it included the last rib and the first four lumbar vertebrae.
- 3. Leg:** The leg was removed by cutting between the 4th and 5th lumbar vertebrae.

4. Rack: The rack was removed by a cut line between the 5th and 6th rib. It contained the portion of seven ribs.

5. Shoulder: The shoulder was obtained by cutting between the 5th and 6th rib, and longitudinal line that crossed the scapula and removed the scapular cartilage. It contains the cervical vertebrae, the boned part of scapula and 5 ribs and the arm.

6. Breast: The lamb breast includes the ventral part of carcass. It contains the ventral portions of the ribs costal cartilage, breast bone a (sternum) and fore shank, and the diaphragm muscle.

Chemical Analysis

Samples of Sorghum Straw, experimental rations and meat samples were proximately analyzed according to Association of Official Analytical Chemists AOAC, (1980).

Statistical Verifications

All the data of the experiments were statistically analyzed by analyses of variance applicable to completely randomized designs (Steel and Torrie, 1980) by using the computer with SPSS program *ver.23* and Duncan multiple range tests was used to detect difference between means (Snedecor and Cochran, 1980).

Results and Discussion

Experimental Animal Performance

The health of the experimental animals was observed to be apparently normal throughout the experimental period. The feedlot performance values of experimental lambs fed shown in **table (4)**. The study showed no significant differences ($P \geq 0.05$) among the different experimental groups for initial body weight, daily feed intake and daily feed intake as % of live body weight values were (23.47, 23.40 and 23.43), (1.22, 1.121 and 1.20) and (3.81, 3.76 and 3.84) that is refer to the similarity of conditions of experiment and ration ingredients. This gives good ground and attentions for using ration incorporated 20% SS for fattening meat animals. Mohana, 2018, Abd Elgadeem, 2019, Hagam, 2020, Babiker, 2020 Ibrahim, 2020, Hassan *et. al.*, 2024 and Mohammed *et. al.*, (2024) reported the same trend. On other hand the study showed a high significant difference ($P < 0.05$) among the different experimental groups for final body weight, total live body weight gain, total live body weight gain as percentage of live body weight and daily weight gain. Treatment B (received 20%SS) tended to recorded the highest values (32.19, 8.79, 26.88 and 0.20 respectively) while treatment C (received 30%SS) reported the less values. The overall mean of results reflects positive effects of ration and lamb performance during exponential periods. Although feed conversion rate numerically, showed high significant difference for treatment A (received no SS) however, treatment B reported the best values which gives preferences for feed intake and live body weight gain. The study agreed with, Hassan *et. al.*, (2024), Mohammed *et. al.*, (2024), Mohana, 2018, Abd Elgadeem, 2019 and Hagam, 2020).

Table 4. Effect of Dietary Incorporation Different Levels of Sorghum Straw on Performance of Desert Sheep (Shuguor Ecotype)

Sorghum straw levels	Experimental groups			Sig
	A (0% SS)	B (20% SS)	C (30% SS)	
Experimental animals, (head)	9.00	9.00	9.00	NS
Experimental periods, (days)	45.00	45.00	45.00	NS
Initial body weight, (kg)	23.33±0.02	23.40±0.03	23.31±0.05	NS
Final body weight, (kg)	31.95±0.03 ^b	32.19±0.28 ^a	31.04±0.01 ^c	**
Total live weight gain, (Kg)	8.69±0.04 ^a	8.79±0.09 ^a	7.73±0.16 ^b	**

Total gain as % of live weight	26.60±0.21 ^a	26.88±0.21 ^a	24.77±0.40 ^b	**
Daily weight gain, (kg)	0.19±0.01 ^a	0.20±0.01	0.17±0.01 ^b	**
Daily feed intake, (kg)	1.22±0.01	1.21±0.02	1.20±0.01	NS
Daily feed intake as % of live body weight	3.81±0.03	3.76±0.07	3.84±0.04	NS
Feed conversion rate (FCR)	7.26±0.02 ^a	6.26±0.29 ^b	6.96±0.28 ^b	*

Note: SS = Sorghum Straw, LS = Level of significance, SE = Standard error, NS = No significantly different * = Significant different at 0.05 ** = Significant different at 0.001 and means in columns followed by the same letter subscript are not significantly different).

Experimental Lamb's Carcass Characteristics

Table (5) depicts the least square means of carcass yield and carcass characteristics of experimental lambs fed different levels of SS. Treatment effects was not significantly differences ($P>0.05$) among the different experimental groups for shoulder, (25.18,25.04 and 24.79) loin (11.42 11.18 and 11.84), breast (11.63. 11.38 and 11.62), fat (14.86.14.38 and 15) and connective tissues (5.45, 4.56 and 4.53) as percentage of hot carcass weight while the study observed high significant differences ($P\leq 0.01$) among the different experimental groups for hot carcass weight (15.77. 16.11 and 15.20), dressing percentage on live body weight (49.55. 49.87 and 48.73), dressing percentage on empty body weight (61.63. 62.38 and 61.16), leges (30.65, 31.66 and 28.72), muscles (57.50, 59.18 and 57.63) and bone (22.19, 21.60 and 21.44) as percentage of hot carcass weight. Lambs fed diet containing 20% of SS was the most superiorly than other groups while lambs feed diet containing 30% of SS were the least. Although the study showed no significant differences ($p<0.05$) among the treatments, still treatment B and treatment A tend to have the best values of carcass yield. On the other hand, treatment B reported the highest values of carcass characteristics namely dressing out percentage on live body weight, dressing out percentage on empty body weight and muscles percentage and this gives preferences to treatment B. The result agreed with Abd Elgadeem, 2019, Hagam,2020, Babiker, 2020 Ibrahim, 2020, Hassan *et. al.*,2024 and Mohammed *et.al.*, (2024) while Mohana, 2018, Hassan *et.al.*, (2013) reported the less values of carcass characteristics.

Table 5. Effect of Dietary Incorporation of Sorghum Straw on Wholesale Cuts as % of Carcass and Carcass Components Desert Sheep (Shuguor Ecotype)

Sorghum straw levels	Experimental groups			Sig
	A (0% SS)	B (20% SS)	C (30% SS)	
Dressing % (on live body weight)	49.55±0.02 ^a	49.87±0.08 ^a	48.73±0.03 ^b	**
Dressing % (on empty body weight)	61.63±0.17 ^b	62.38±0.14 ^a	61.16±0.20 ^b	**
Hot carcass weight,(kg)	15.77±0.03 ^b	16.11±0.06 ^a	15.20±0.05 ^c	***
Legs, (%)	30.65±0.18 ^a	31.66±0.23 ^a	28.72±0.71 ^a	**
Shoulder, (%)	25.18±0.80	25.04±0.23	24.79±0.1	NS
Loin, (%)	11.42±0.34	11.18±0.04	11.84±0.04	NS
Breast (%)	11.63±0.40	11.38±0.21	11.62±0.25	NS
Rack, (%)	11.63±0.20	11.38±0.21	11.38±0.21	NS
Neck, (%)	6.34±0.01	6.01±0.20	6.57±0.39	NS
Tail, (%)	3.38±0.21	3.35±0.43	3.42±0.40	NS
Muscles, (%)	57.50±0.28 ^b	59.18±0.06 ^a	57.63±0.08 ^b	**
Bone, (%)	22.19±0.09 ^a	21.60±0.05 ^{ab}	21.44±0.29 ^b	*
Fat, (%)	14.86±0.02	14.38±0.16	15.00±0.57	NS
Connective tissues, (%)	5.45±0.23	4.56±0.22	4.53±0.31	NS

Economic and Benefit of Experimental Rations

Economic study and benefit showed in table (6). The study observed that treatment B reported the best values of feed conversion rate (6.26), cost of one kg ration (670 SG) and cost of one Kg meat (4316SG) compared to other groups (A and C) this gives attention and promising vision of using Sorghum Straw through wide scales to increase the cost of fattening.

Table 6. Effect of Using Dietary Incorporated Different Levels of Sorghum Straw on Economic Study of Desert Sheep (Shuguor Ecotype)

Sorghum straw levels	Experimental groups			Sig
	A (0% SS)	B (20% SS)	C (30% SS)	
Feed conversion rate (FCR)	7.26±0.01 ^a	6.26±0.17 ^b	6.96±0.16 ^a	**
Cost of one kg ration, (SDG)	860±11.54 ^a	670±5.97 ^b	690±11.54 ^b	**
Cost of one Kg meat, (SDG)	5756±277.14 ^a	4316±95.97 ^b	4666±105.88 ^b	**

Note: SS = Sorghum Straw, LS = Level of significance, SE = Standard error, NS = No significantly different * = Significant different at 0.05 ** = Significant different at 0.001 and mean in columns followed by the same letter subscript are not significantly different).

Conclusion and Recommendation

According to results of present study It was concluded that the addition of 20% SS recorded the highest values of live body weight, carcass yield and carcass characteristic compared with other treatment groups, therefore the study recommended to use ration incorporated 20% SS for fattening desert lambs.

Acknowledgements

Great thanks, sincere appreciation and deep gratitude to Commission of Scientific Research and Innovation, Ministry of High Education and Scientific Research, Sudan for financing research project grant. All so thanks extended to Faculty of animal production, University of Gezira, Sudan.

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